

Common Fixed Point Theorems for Co-cyclic Weak Contractions in Compact Metric

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Abstract : In this paper, we prove some common fixed point theorems for co-cyclic ϕ -weak contractions in compact metric spaces. Examples are also given in support of our results.

Keywords : Co-cyclic ϕ -weak contraction, Co-cyclic representation, Common fixed point.

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